

Guide to Designing Digital Research Skills Training Materials: Textual Materials

Reading time: 30 minutes

Skills and Workforce Development Team

Australian Research Data Commons

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Introduction

The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) *Guide to Designing Digital Research Skills Training Materials: Textual Materials* aims to support training materials creators, trainers and national training infrastructure providers in the creation of textual guides while also encouraging the sharing and reuse of their training materials. It aims to facilitate the design, development and delivery of textual guides on digital research and data skills in alignment with best practices in learning and training.

This tool is informed by the [Universal Design for Learning](#) principles which aims to eliminate barriers in the design of learning materials to make content accessible to all.

Benefits of Accessible Learning Materials

We all learn differently. When we create learning materials that are mindful of the needs of a diverse range of audiences – be it English as an Additional Language (EAL), differently abled or neurodivergent learners – we are also creating learning materials that benefit all. In supporting a wider learner range, accessible learning materials:

- encourage reuse
- are more readily usable with the things they need to know and will learn made explicit
- reduce the need to create multiple versions of the same training for people with different needs
- reduce stigma
- promote equity.

Is What You're Delivering Being Received the Same Way?

There is often a gap between the information we deliver and what is received. We often forget about the tacit knowledge that enables us to readily understand a topic we are already familiar with. Learners often lack such tacit knowledge.

In creating learner-centred materials, a mindset shift is needed: the delivery should align with the reception, not the other way round. We need to be deliberate and explicit in presenting the information, especially when the target audience might be encountering the topic for the first time, coming from a different language background, or contending with challenges they prefer not to discuss.

GOOD PRACTICES	THINGS TO AVOID
Focus on how learners might receive the information.	Assume all learners automatically understand the ideas.
Consider learners' background knowledge.	Use metaphors or technical language without explaining them.
Be deliberate – state points and ideas explicitly.	Expect the reader to make inferences.
Include different forms of representations (such as diagrams, pictures and concept maps).	Use too much text or extended prose.

Who Is This Tool For?

- Subject matter experts who create textual guides
- People interested in writing guides

Prior Knowledge

Familiarity with writing guides is not necessary for understanding this self-assessment tool. The tool specifically aims to help those who are new to writing guides.

FAIR Data

The ARDC has developed [a Training Materials Metadata Checklist](#). It aims to help learning designers, training materials creators, trainers and national training infrastructure providers capture key information and apply appropriate mechanisms to make their training materials sharable and reusable.

Use the checklist to enact FAIR!

Textual Guide Checklist

The textual guide checklist is a companion tool that ensures that your guide takes into account the key points of this document. It comprises 2 sections – format and content considerations. Refer to the

corresponding sections of this document for examples of the elements and what the features, indicators, or descriptors mean.

You can use this checklist:

- before you start writing your guide to get an idea of how to approach it
- after you have written your guide to ensure you've addressed the various elements.

FORMAT			
No.	Elements	Descriptors	Tick if evident
1	Readability	Use your organisation's template and follow their branding guidelines.	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The typeface is easy to read. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The typeface is large enough. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The colour contrast for both the text and the images is strong enough. 	
2	Images – pictures, diagrams, graphs, concept maps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All (non-decorative) images are captioned or described. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The link between the image and the explanation is clear. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideas and concepts are represented visually where possible. 	
3	Language	Refer to your organisation's editorial style guide (if available).	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Explain all acronyms and abbreviations explained in full. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use the active voice. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use plain English. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Links: link specific calls-to-action to the intended destinations and put them at the end of 	

FORMAT			
No.	Elements	Descriptors	Tick if evident
		sentences. Use concise keywords for the text and avoid generic phrases like “click here”.	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Numbers: use numerals for 2 and above. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain all technical terms. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a glossary (for guides with 6 or more technical terms). 	
4	Chunking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Similar ideas are grouped together. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long paragraphs have been broken into smaller ones. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sentences with more than 2 points or ideas have been rewritten for simplicity. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bullet points are used, where possible. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Headings and subheadings are used, where possible. 	
5	Consistency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the same names and terminology throughout the guide. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formatting (formats, fonts, colours) is consistent. 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Left aligned throughout. 	

CONTENT			
No.	Elements	Descriptors	Tick if evident
7	Orientation	Expected time needed to go through the guide is stated	
		Prior knowledge needed to understand the guide is clearly identified	
		Purpose of the guide is outlined	
		Outcomes are clearly stated	
		Target audience is stated	
		Overview of areas to be discussed are listed	
5	Exemplification	Examples follow explanations.	
		Current and relevant examples	
		Authentic samples (such as screenshots) are provided as examples, where possible.	
8	Closing	Key ideas are summarised	
		Key points are recapped and presented as bullet points	
		Cheat sheet is included (where the content is complex or heavy)	
		Further information directions are stated	
		Call-to-action is clearly listed (if applicable)	
9	Review	Templates or editable resources are included.	
		Trial the draft guide.	
		Approvals are met.	

CONTENT			
No.	Elements	Descriptors	Tick if evident
10	Share	Follow your organisation’s guidelines for the sharing of resources.	
		Consider sharing your resource through Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA) .	

Elements Explained

The following sections explain the elements of a good textual guide’s design and format and its content, respectively. These are particularly useful for those who are putting a guide together for the first time, need a refresher or would like to clarify their understanding of the descriptors in the textual guide checklist.

Format Considerations

How you format your guide can impact its accessibility. The following elements are considerations for designing a more reader-friendly guide.

1. Readability

Make sure there is high contrast between the colour of your text and images and that of their background. High colour contrast reduces eye strain and helps readers focus.

Figure 1. Colour contrast in text

Source: <https://www.smashingmagazine.com/2017/01/underestimated-power-color-mobile-app-design/>

Figure 2 (next page). Colour combination visibility chart

Source: <https://visualdisplaylearninglog.wordpress.com/2014/10/27/the-use-of-colours/>

2. Images – pictures, diagrams, graphs, concept maps

Captions or descriptions for images

Labelling images with a caption or description reduces cognitive load by providing a clear reference point and explicitly stating the relationship between the image and the explanation. Caption or describe non-decorative images (images that are, in some way related to the text, not those placed for aesthetic purposes) in your guide.

Figure 3. Examples of a caption (circled in red)

Table 1 Spring Blossoms

Colour Family	Bulbs	Shrubs	Trees
Pink	Tulips	Flowering current	Ornamental plum
Yellow	Daffodils	Forsythia	Star magnolia

Source: p. 69, 2021_Gray Universal_Design for Learning Course Book

Figure 4. Examples of a description (circled in red)

Source: *SPDX Licence Identifier Guide*

Clear link between image and explanation

Except for decorative images, learners should not be left to guess the point of the image. Refer to the image in your explanation, or label the image so learners understand its purpose.

Visual representation of ideas and concepts

Concept maps are a useful way to represent related concepts and help learners understand relationships between different things. They can take the form of charts, graphic organisers, tables, flowcharts, Venn Diagrams and timelines. Consider using a concept map to offer learners another way of thinking about concepts.

Visual collaboration tools like [Miro](#) allow you to brainstorm ideas and create concept maps.

3. Language

The [Australian Government Style Manual](#), a writing guide based on evidence and best practice in the Australian context, offers good tips on writing style.

Aim to create a textual guide that can be understood by a diverse audience after one reading.

Plain English

Use plain English to convey information clearly and confidently. The language should be simple and to the point. It should be understood after one reading.

Principles of plain English include using:

- familiar, everyday words
- active voice
- personal pronouns such as “you” and “we”
- sentences with simple structures and no longer than 25 words.

Read more about [why short sentences are important](#).

Read more about [plain English and word choice](#).

Active voice

Plain English uses the active voice, in which the subject of a sentence is clearly the actor. An active sentence follows a formula the reader can more easily process: subject–verb–object.

- Active voice: “The boy threw the ball.”
- Passive voice: “The ball was thrown by the boy.”

The word “by” is often found in passive sentences.

Using personal pronouns like “you” and “we” at the start of the sentence helps you write in an active voice. You’re less likely to write “the ball was thrown by you” than “you threw the ball”.

Read more about [the active voice and how to identify passive writing](#).

Acronyms and abbreviations

Avoid acronyms and abbreviations where possible. If you need to use one, spell it out in the first instance before introducing it in brackets, and then use the acronym consistently in the rest of the document.

E.g. and i.e.

Rather than using “e.g.” or “i.e.”, write “for example” and “that is” instead, particularly in more formal publications.

If you can’t avoid using “e.g.” or “i.e.”, remember to include a full stop after each letter. This helps screen readers announce them.

Don’t use a comma after “e.g.” or “i.e.” as you would after “for example” or “that is”.

Et cetera, etc.

Try not to use “et cetera” or “etc. Instead, use “and so on” with a comma before it.

“Etc.” is redundant in a list introduced by “for example”, “such as” or “including”. These expressions already show that the list is incomplete.

If you think you need to use “etc.” because there’s more to say, try to include those ideas in your sentence instead.

Read more about [abbreviations](#).

Links

Choosing the right hyperlink text and placing it correctly are important for accessibility reasons. This is particularly so for people relying on screen readers to consume digital content.

Link specific **calls-to-action** to their intended destinations.

Use concise keywords for call-to-action text or buttons. Accurately describe what will happen when the reader clicks on the link, and **avoid generic phrases**.

- Write: “[Start your application](#)”
- Don’t write: “Click [here](#) to apply”

Read more about [links](#).

Numbers

Use numerals for 2 and above.

Technical terms

Technical terms might not be understood by the audience, especially if they are new to the area. You could explain all technical terms in the guide or refer the audience to an external resource to help them understand what you mean.

Glossary

If there are 6 or more technical terms in the guide, you might want to include a glossary for ease of reference and to increase accessibility.

Figure 5 (next page). Example of a glossary

Data Augmentation - a technique to artificially increase the amount of training data from existing training data without actually collecting new data.

Data Joins - combining multiple data tables based on a common field between them or "a key." There are 6 types of join: inner, left inner, left outer, right inner, right outer and outer.

Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) - the intercompany exchange of business documents in a standard electronic format between business partners.

NoSQL - non-relational database that stores and retrieves data without needing to define its structure first - an alternative to the more rigid relational database model. Instead of storing data in rows and columns like a traditional database, a NoSQL database stores each item individually with a unique key.

PostgreSQL - a free and open-source object-relational database management system emphasizing extensibility and SQL compliance. It's the fourth most popular database in the world.

Rust (programming language) - a static multi-paradigm, memory-efficient, open-source programming language that is focused on speed, security, and performance. Rust blends the performance of languages such as C++ with friendlier syntax, a focus on code safety and a well-engineered set of tools that simplify development.

Source: <https://www.osmos.io/blog/data-terms-glossary-list>

4. Chunking

Difficult to understand

When a sentence has too many parts, contains two or more ideas, or has too many conditionals, the cognitive load on the reader is amplified as they have to work extra hard to identify the discrete parts before connecting them up again and making sense of the part-whole relationship. The load is further compounded by the use of technical words, acronyms, unexplained abbreviations, complicated sentence structures, figurative language and unconnected ideas, and more so when the sentence is written in the passive voice. And if this were not enough, consider how this long, rambling, convoluted paragraph looks as opposed to the bullet points below, which require far less mental acrobatics and look more manageable at first glance regardless of how familiar or unfamiliar the topic is to the reader.

Easier to understand

Group similar ideas together so readers can make connections more easily. Restrict sentences to no

more than 2 points or ideas each. The shorter the paragraph or sentence, the easier it is to understand. Headings and subheadings help readers keep track of their reading and contextualise parts of the content against the whole.

Easiest to understand

Better yet, use bullet points like so:

- Similar ideas are grouped together.
- Long paragraphs are broken into smaller ones.
- Sentences with more than 2 points or ideas are rewritten for simplicity.
- Bullet points are used, where possible.
- Headings and subheadings are used, where possible.

5. Consistency

Naming

Use the same terminology and names throughout. If you start off the guide by referring to your readers as “reader”, switch midway to “learner”, and mix these up occasionally with “participant” or “SME”, they need to spend extra effort and time to make sense of what you’re saying and if you’re referring to the same thing.

Formatting

Once your brain is set up to encounter content in a particular format, any variation to the format requires additional effort. Keep formats, fonts and colours as familiar as possible to reduce unnecessary cognitive load.

Text alignment

Align the text left (instead of justifying it) throughout your guide. This makes it more accessible to neuro-divergent readers.

Content Considerations

The next few elements focus on helping readers make sense of the content in the guide. These are particularly useful for longer guides:

6. Orientation

Framing new content with information about it helps the audience to better engage with it and increases opportunities for knowledge retention. By explicitly stating information about the content before presenting it, learners can decide if the resource suits their needs at the start.

Expected time

Learners should be provided with an indication of time needed to work through the guide. This reduces the burden on learners to figure out how much time they need to invest and helps them set aside time to read the guide.

Most learners read at a rate of 200 to 250 words per minute, plus 12 seconds for the first image, 11 seconds for the second image, and so on. If the content is highly technical or if there are many new concepts, increase the reading time to account for the additional cognitive load.

Now, let's say your guide is estimated to take 20 minutes to read. You could include one of the following at the start of the guide after the title to indicate the approximate reading time:

- "Reading time: 20 minutes"
- "20-minute read"

Prior knowledge

New knowledge is built on prior knowledge. Explicitly stating assumed prior knowledge helps increase opportunity for learner success and empowers learners to:

- gauge the difficulty level
- identify their existing knowledge gaps, if any
- decide if they need a knowledge refresh before engaging with new content

Here are some examples of how you can inform learners of the kinds of prior knowledge needed to understand the guide:

Example 1

Prior knowledge needed: You will need a good understanding of your project purpose and what it will achieve, and your target audience groups.

Example 2

Assumed prior knowledge:

To understand this guide, learners need to be familiar with:

1. Basic Command Line terms
2. Launching and connecting to an Instance via SSH
3. Using software or the command line to move files between instance and local computer

Source: *Sonia Ramza*

Purpose of the guide

Outlining the purpose of the guide allows the learner to decide if the guide is relevant and understand how the guide can help them. A useful question to consider is why learners should care about this topic. Explaining the purpose and importance of the topic creates learner buy-in, which helps them be more receptive to the content.

Example 1

WHY?

Improving the communication of European research infrastructures is an essential step towards their sustainability. For this, there is a need to consolidate the very concept of “research infrastructures”, improve how different stakeholders perceive them and increase their visibility. The common use of this toolkit by the different research infrastructures in Europe is expected to harmonize their communications - basically, to ensure that they “speak the same language” and effectively engage with different sectors.

Source: [RI-VIS Communication Toolkit](#)

Example 2

Figure 6 (next page). Example of an outline of a guide’s purpose

Source: ARDC Research Software Rights Management Guide

Outcomes

Stating the target outcomes helps the audience frame their knowledge, focus on the topic and assess their learning progress. Present each outcome separately for ease of identification. It is not necessary to describe the process leading to the outcome.

Poor example

Toolkit outcomes:

1. Discuss and collaborate to agree on a communication strategy for the project.
2. Identify the primary and secondary target audiences and collate words to use when communicating about the project.
3. Brainstorm desired communication tactics and channels for communicating with your target audiences.

Good example

Toolkit outcomes:

1. a communication strategy for your project
2. target audiences identified
3. words to use when talking or writing about your project with your target audiences
4. communication tactics and channels for communicating with your target audiences

Target audience

Explicitly stating the target audience helps the audience quickly identify if the guide is relevant to them. Consider the audience level your guide targets and how much technical understanding the audience has.

Let's say your guide is developed for researchers. In that case, explicitly mention them in this section as an audience to show that the guide is for them. Also consider the differences in, say, the degree of technical knowledge, career level, and field of research among researchers. You may want to specify the subgroups your guide is for.

Example

Who is this guide for?

- Research software engineers
- Data stewards

Source: SPDX licence identifier guide

Overview

An overview of the content that will be covered helps the audience develop a mental schema of the various parts of the content. It helps them track how much they have learned and what else they will need to learn. While we're focusing on what the audience can gain from it when we talk about the outcomes of a guide, the overview is about providing the audience with a quick breakdown of the content.

A contents page can often provide the learner with an overview of what will be covered. Check that your headings and subheadings are at the right levels if you want your word processor to generate the contents page for you. Using wrong heading levels will lead to the table of contents being presented in a wrong hierarchy and affect understanding.

If your guide is brief and you don't intend to include a contents page, consider listing the areas to be covered to prepare your audience.

Example

This guide aims to cover the following areas:

- accessible learning materials: what do I need to think about?
- formatting user-centric textual guides
- content design in user-centric textual guides
- next steps: what do I do now that I've finished writing the guide?

7. Exemplification

Modelling what to do through examples helps the audience understand new content in a concrete way. Use authentic or contextualised examples as far as possible for greater resonance. Examples that are current and relevant to the audience’s real work situations contribute to meaningful content. Screen shots and other authentic samples also allow readers to understand what you mean more quickly through a worked example.

Figure 7. Example of exemplification

Popular Open-Source Licences

Permissive	Copyleft (Weak)	Copyleft (Strong)
Apache 2.0	LGPL v3	GPL v3
BSD 3-Clause	Mozilla Public Licence 2	GPL v2
MIT		

Source: [ARDC Research Software Rights Management Guide](#)

8. Closing

How you close the guide is as important as how it opens. Audiences tend to remember what happened first (primacy), what happened last (recency), and the unusual. An effective closing sets learners up to apply what they have learned in a meaningful way.

Help the audience achieve a sense of closure through the following:

Summarise key ideas

New knowledge is built upon existing knowledge. Summarising the areas discussed allows the audience to consolidate what they have learned and organise their new knowledge in a meaningful context.

Recap key points

Help learners recall key takeaways by presenting these as bullet points. Think of it this way: assuming the audience didn't have the time to go through the guide, what are the very least they should know?

Example

YOU'VE COMPLETED THE TOOLKIT!

Congratulations on completing the ARDC Communication and Engagement Toolkit!

In this toolkit you have:

- described your project key communication goals, messages and audience
- investigated different communication tools and tactics
- crafted a communication plan around the phases and milestones of your project
- reviewed tips for evaluating your communication.

Cheat sheet

If the content in the guide is highly technical, complicated or long, consider including a cheat sheet at the end. A cheat sheet is a quick reference resource and should not be more than one page long.

Example (next page)

nectarcloud
Resource Sheet

 support.ehelp.edu.au

Navigating the Dashboard. **Command Line Terms**

Managing Key Pairs

Project > Compute > Key Pairs

Security Groups

Project > Network > Security Groups

Creating a Volume

Project > Volume > Volumes

Manage your instances

Project > Computer > Instances

ls list all files

mkdir new folder

touch <file name> - create a new file

pwd - show the file path of your current location

rm <file name> - remove a file

rmdir <folder> remove a folder

cd change directory

Nano your text editor

Connecting on the Command Line

```
ssh -i ~/ssh/trainingkeyname ubuntu@insert.ip.address.here
```

Keyword Definitions

Virtual Machine/Instance: a term used to describe your cloud computer.

Availability Zone: this is the physical data centre location where an instance resides.

Flavor: a flavor sets up the size of a collection of virtual machine components, such as memory and CPU. You can't select the size of these components individually, but select a flavour type (example: small, medium, large) which sets the size of each component appropriately.

Image: a file that contains an operating system, which is added to a blank instance.

SSH: This is short for Secure Shell. It is a way to setup an encrypted (secure) connection between your computer and the cloud computer, usually via the command line.

Backup: Copy of your Data

Snapshot: Copy of your computer settings, apps and configurations and root disk (not other data on volumes)

Source: Sonia Ramza, ARDC

Further information

You should also provide the audience with contact information in case they want to learn more. If appropriate, direct them to additional resources.

Example

We'd like to hear from you! How did you use this toolkit? What did you like about it? What could be improved? Let us know comms@ardc.edu.au.

Contact us. If you have questions about the content of this toolkit or would like assistance, please contact the ARDC Communication and Marketing team via comms@ardc.edu.au.

Call to action

Include specific actions you would like the audience to take at the end of the guide.

Example

What should researchers do after reading this guide?

- Find relevant training on Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA)
- Look for upcoming Carpentries workshops.
- Make contact with [community].

9. Review

Congratulations! Your guide is ready – it's now time to review it. At this stage, you want to finetune your draft and ensure that there are no gaps in the communication loop.

Templates and editable resources

For easy access, include at the end of the guide any editable resources that could be useful to the audience or that they need to complete. These resources could include templates, forms and checklists.

Trial draft guide

Test how your guide is actually received by trialling it with an audience!

To get feedback on the content and the user experience, you could ask the audience:

1. What do you remember best about this guide? Or what are 3 things you remember after reading this guide?

2. Which parts of the guide were most useful?
3. What were the areas you found challenging?
4. What are some things that would make them less challenging? Or what would help fix that?

Trialling the guide with people who have little background knowledge in the area and asking them to teach back (tell you what the guide is about and what they learned from it) would help reveal areas in the guide that need to be more explicit, whether it be the key terms, key concepts or steps involved.

At the same time, trialling the guide with other subject matter experts is useful in challenging your own assumptions and highlighting areas which might have been overlooked.

Consider how often the guide will be reviewed after its publication and who will review it.

Approvals

It's a good idea to share the guide with your team and get feedback on it. It's also worth finding out if your organisation has specific guidelines on the approval process, who you can share the guide with and how to share it.

10. Sharing

Sharing through your organisation

Are there organisational guidelines for the sharing of guides and learning resources? Your organisation might have its own channels through which you could share your guide. It might also be worth finding out if there are guidelines to follow before you share your guide more widely.

Sharing through DReSA

Ready to share your guide with the broader community? Help the community find you and your resource more easily by entering details that describe and provide access to your resource in [DReSA](#).

You can also create a [trainer profile in DReSA](#) to increase visibility of your skills and help the community locate you.

Resources

Here's a quick recap of the resources we referred to in this document:

- [the ARDC Training Materials Metadata Checklist](#) for enacting FAIR
- [the Australian Government Style Manual](#) for learning the best practice for writing in the Australian context
 - the Manual's page on [plain English and word choice](#)
 - the Manual's page on [active voice and how to identify passive writing](#)
 - the Manual's page on [abbreviations](#)
- an article on [why short sentences are important](#)
- the visual collaboration tool [Miro](#)
- [Digital Research Skills Australasia \(DReSA\)](#).

Further Information

To find out more about Universal Design for Learning (UDL), read the following:

- [Universal Design for Learning \(UDL\)](#), developed by CAST
- a one-page summary of [Universal Design](#) by [the Centre for Universal Design Australia](#)
- NSW Government's [Universal Design for Learning planning tool](#)
- [Universal Design for Learning in Tertiary Education](#) (for education staff working in the Higher Education and the Vocational Education and Training sectors).

We'd Like to Hear From You!

How did you use this self-assessment tool? What did you like about it? What could be improved? Let us know contact@ardc.edu.au.

Contact us

If you have questions about the content of this self-assessment tool, or would like assistance, please contact the ARDC Skills and Workforce Development team via contact@ardc.edu.au.